

INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL AND SOCIAL PERFORMANCE OF ETHIOPIAN MICROFINANCE INSTITUTIONS

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Received: Feb 15, 2026

Accepted: Mar 18, 2026

Published: Mar 20, 2026

Abstract

Purpose: *The main objectives of the study are to examine the relationship between intellectual Capital and the social performance of MFIs. More specifically, to examine the effects of individual constituents of intellectual Capital, such as human Capital, structural Capital, and Capital employed, on the social performance(outreach) of MFIs in Ethiopia.*

Methodology: *The current study utilised an explanatory research design with quantitative research. Panel data from 21 registered MFIs for a period of 10 years were used between 2015 and 2024. The study used Panel data analysis in order to examine the link between intellectual Capital and its components with MFI social performance.*

Finding; *the result reveals that on aggregate value-added intellectual Capital had favourable and statistically substantial effect on total client served(outreach) ($\beta = 0.1805$, $p = 0.028$) from the elements of intellectual Capital, Human capital efficiency (HCE) exhibited a strong and significant positive relationship with client outreach ($\beta = 0.327$, $p = 0.034$), emphasizing the essential role of staff knowledge, enthusiasm, and output in expanding the client base. On the other hand, Capital employed efficiency, and structural Capital Efficiency had an insignificant association with client outreach.*

Originality: *This study is the first to examine the impact of intellectual Capital on the social performance of microfinance institutions in the context of Ethiopia.*

Theoretical implications: *The findings of the study support the opinion that intellectual capital in general and human capital in particular are vital factors of social performance in microfinance institutions. This highlights the relevance of the resource-based view (RBV) and knowledge-based theory (KBT) in explaining performance differences among MFIs operating in developing economies such as Ethiopia.*

Practical implications: *The manager of MFI gives priorities in human capital investments via providing capacity building, staff training, and other fringe benefits so that productivity and client outreach will improve. As a policy maker and regulator of financial institutions, the National Bank of Ethiopia should offer different initiatives, like digital capability and innovations within MFI, to enhance social performance (client outreach).*

Key Words; *Intellectual capital; social performance; microfinance institutions; Ethiopia.*

I. INTRODUCTION

During the age of industrialism, tangible assets such as plants, estates, and equipment were the primary sources of value for the enterprise. However, with the advent of globalisation and technological advances, much interest has been directed to the more knowledge-intensive areas of enterprises as vital sources of strategic capital. This required recognition and effective management of intangibles, collectively known as intellectual capital (Nicolescu & Nicolescu, 2021) Intellectual capital is now considered a very important catalyst for competitive advantage, innovation, and the ability of enterprises to maintain continuous vitality.

intellectual capital is divided into three primary elements: human capital, structural capital, and capital efficiency (Muhammad & Ismail, 2009; Pulic, 2000). Human capital consists of the skills, abilities, creativity, and experience of a company's personnel and is a renewable store of knowledge and innovation (Bontis, 1998). Structural capital denotes the institutionalised knowledge found in processes, databases, organisational culture, and information systems, which are the means that really exist in the company, notwithstanding

personnel (Edvinsson, 1996). Capital employed efficiency, which is not so well recognised as either human or structural capital, but is of equal importance and pertains to the efficient use of the physical and financial assets that are involved in the making use of both fixed and floating capital, all of which is done in the business processes (Pulic, 2000). It indicates how efficiently the tangible capital has been used by the enterprise in conjunction with its intangibles. The efficiency of capital employed has a good posterior, along with the financial performance and value of the enterprise, which is further proved by some of the research indicating that it has a large impact as regards the values to be obtained in a consideration of the factors of intellectual capital (Sulaiman et al., 2021).

The Resource-Based View (RBV) and Knowledge-Based Theory serve as the primary frameworks for comprehending intellectual capital (IC). Both viewpoints underscore the significance of knowledge as an intangible asset that enhances a firm's performance (Jay Barney, 1991). Resource-based theory posits that both tangible and intangible assets are fundamental company resources that drive competitiveness and enhance performance (Riahi-Belkaoui, 2003). Companies utilize both tangible assets, such as property, plant, and equipment, and intangible assets, such as intellectual capital, for their operational activities, competitiveness, and profitability. Nonetheless, owing to their uniqueness and non-substitutable intangible assets, intellectual capital is seen as a strategic asset that facilitates higher performance for the organization (Jay Barney, 1991).

Microfinance institutions (MFIs) specifically in low-income countries like Ethiopia have two main objectives: financial sustainability and increased social outreach towards economically deprived individuals (Ahamad et al., 2023; Remer & Kattilakoski, 2021). In achieving these objectives, intellectual capital is vital. The management of human capital, structural capital, and capital employed efficiency in MFIs offers opportunities to innovate, expand operations, and optimize resource allocation to increase social outreach and improve financial sustainability. Recent research has established that intellectual capital and its components are important determinants of MFIs' performance. (Ahamad et al., 2023) Point out that the efficiency of capital employed in operations, along with the efficiencies of human and structural capital, shows significant enhancement in the social outreach and financial viability of MFIs. (Githaiga et al., 2023) Further, the efficiency of

capital employed significantly improves resource allocation in MFIs, thereby enabling them to provide financial services to low-income earners. Therefore, we understood that the three elements of intellectual capital are vital, whether individually or collectively, and that they also improve the outreach and sustainability of the MFI.

We have examined several studies that examined the direct link between intellectual capital and performance across diverse countries and industries. For instance, Bhatia & Aggarwal, (2015) explored this relationship in the Indian public sector. (Nawaz & Haniffa, 2017). focus on banks existing globally. Priti Sharma, (2019) analysed their studies of Indian BSE S&P 500 Listed Firms. Xu & Liu (2020) assess Korean manufacturing companies. Haque & Weqar, (2021) examine Indian companies listed on the Standard and Poor Bombay Stock Exchange Sensitive Index. Tahir et al., (2021) focused on Pakistan banks . Lee et al., (n.d.) on Vietnamese commercial banks. Vetchagool, (2023) on Agro and food industries in Thailand. Further, Costa et al., (2022) conducted their studies on Brazilian firms, and Rong et al., (2025) examined banks within the European Union. These studies, taken together, provide vital empirical evidence on intellectual capital and performance across sectors and countries.

However, research on microfinance institutions remains very limited globally. Githaiga et al., (2023) examined financial sustainability and intellectual capital. Ahamad et al., (2023) examine both financial and social efficiency of MFIs. In the context of developing countries, Peñarreta Quezada & Chavez Alvear, (2025) in Ecuador and Kamukama et al., (2010) in Uganda studied the link between intellectual capital and the financial performance of MFI. However, both studies differed first due to methodological inconsistencies. Kamukama et al., (2010) used primary data in Uganda, while Peñarreta Quezada & Chavez Alvear, (2025) used panel data and the GMM model in Ecuador. Making cross-country comparison difficult and restricting the generalizability of their result. Second, Kamukama et al., (2010) found that all three constitutions of IC have a significant, positive influence on the financial performance of MFIs. At the same time, Peñarreta Quezada & Chavez Alvear, (2025) demonstrate only Human capital and structural capital as major predictors of performance. This shows a contextual variation. In the Ethiopian context, several studies have examined intellectual capital and firm performance in other sectors, notably (Getachew Habtamu, 2023; Girma, 2017; Mekonnen

Akalu, 2024; Moges Adugna & Kumar, 2021), which focused on Ethiopian commercial banks. At the same time, Ayinaddis et al. (2024) examined the insurance companies. Even though extensive research has examined the associations between intellectual capital and firm performance across various countries, industries, and sectors, including banking, manufacturing, insurance, and agro-industries, very few studies have focused on microfinance institutions (MFIs), particularly in developing countries. Moreover, existing studies focus on financial performance while overlooking MFIs' social performance, which is key to their dual missions. Hence, a lack of comprehensive evidence on how intellectual capital and its components affect the social performance of MFIs, especially in developing economies like Ethiopia. where the sector plays a vital role in financial inclusion and poverty alleviation. Addressing this gap by employing the Panel data method will yield valuable insights into how intellectual capital enhances the social performance of Ethiopian MFIs, for which such studies are scarce.

The present article is arranged in the following manner: Section 2, literature review and conceptual framework; Section 3, methodology; Section 4, analysis and discussion.

II. METHODOLOGY AND DATA

The present research was based on an explanatory research design and a quantitative research methodology to investigate the determinants of microfinance institutional performance. This method is popular in empirical research on microfinance since it allows the researcher to examine causal relationships among variables through statistical and econometric methods. A number of recent empirical studies that examine the performance and efficiency of microfinance institutions have taken a similar quantitative and explanatory research design (Asmare Zewdie, 2022; Getaneh Gobezie, 2023; Mersha Debebe, 2024).

This research targets all active and registered microfinance institutions in Ethiopia. As of 2024, 41 MFIs were actively working and providing financial services. However, as some institutions could not provide all and consistent financial data, the study uses only twenty-one MFIs with reliable data. The data was secondary data obtained from the National Bank of Ethiopia and the Association of Ethiopian Microfinance Institutions from 2015 to 2024.

Since the data was longitudinal, the econometric methods used to analyse the correlation between the study variables were panel data Model. The analysis of panel data enables the researcher to account both for unobserved heterogeneity among institutions and to measure cross-sectional and time-series variations (Jeffrey M. Wooldridge, 2021; William H. Greene, 2020). In order to establish the most suitable specification, Hausman specification test was used to compare the individual effects correlated to the explanatory variables. This methodology has become very popular in recent empirical research studies investigating the performance and efficiency of microfinance (Robert Cull et al., 2021; Roy Mersland and R. Oystein Strom, 2022). Accordingly, Random effect model is used based Hausman selection criteria.

INDEPENDENT, DEPENDENT AND CONTROL VARIABLE MEASUREMENTS

Table 1 Variable Measurements

Variables	Measurements	Source/ reference
Dependent variable		
Social performance		((Abera, 2023; Memon et al., 2020)
breadth of outreach	Number of active borrowers.	
Independent variables		
Intellectual capital	Value-added intellectual capital (VAIC) TM	(Pulic, 2000).
Human capital (HC)	HCE/VA	(Pulic, 2000).
Structural capital (SC)	SC/VA	
Capital employed (CE)	CEE/VA	

Control Variable		
Age of the firm	several years since their establishment.	(Xu & Liu, 2020).
Size of firm	Legalism of total asset.	(Ahamad et al., 2023; Memon et al., 2020)
Leverage	The ratio of debt to equity	

Econometric Model

The study examined how intellectual capital and its components affected return on assets and return on equity using panel-data regressions. It was done as described by (Ahamad et al., 2023 and Getachew Habtamu, 2023). We used two distinct regression models. First, VAIC with LogTC went down. Second, we use LogTC to do a regression on VAIC. As a result, the two-panel model is shown below.

Model 1

$$\log TC_{it} = \beta_{it} + \beta_1 \ln VAIC_{IT} + \beta_2 Age_{it} + \beta_3 \log TA_{it} + \beta_4 lever_{it} + u_{it}$$

Model 2

$$\log TC_{it} = \beta_{0it} + \beta_1 \ln VAIC_{IT} + \beta_2 \ln HCE_{IT} + \beta_3 \ln SCE_{IT} + \beta_4 \ln CEE_{IT} + \beta_5 Age_{it} + \beta_6 \log TA_{it} + \beta_7 lever_{it} + u_{it}$$

Were

LogTC indicates total number of clients served

LogVAIC designate for logarithm of Value-added intellectual capital.

LogHCE means logarithm of Human Capital efficiency.

LogSCE displays Logarithm of Structural Capital Efficiency.

LogCEE specifies Logarithm of Capital Employed Efficiency.

Age represents age of the firm since their establishments.

LogTA rerepresent Size of MFI measured By total asset.

lever indicate firms' leverage.

III RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

This paper is intended to assess the impact of intellectual capital on the social performance of Ethiopian microfinance Institutions. Based on secondary data collected, the following section presents descriptive statistics for the study, including the mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation. In addition, it presents the necessary model assumptions, such as heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, correlations, and normality. Lastly, the results of the fixed-effect model presented.

Table 2 Descriptive statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
log_totalclients	210	9.283749	1.871363	3.555348	13.04172
log_VAIC	210	1.121895	0.643731	0.0864009	3.328857
log_CEE	210	0.0581526	0.0733355	0.0004588	0.7154408
log_SCE	210	0.4066582	0.1739367	0.0125583	0.6744128
log_HCE	210	0.9274897	0.6707911	0.012718	3.293598
firmage	210	17.11905	5.918919	1.000000	27.00000
log_TotalAsset	210	12.3139	1.894894	6.440000	16.67000
leverage	210	2.92952	4.464886	0.0333437	61.41056

Source; Authors, 2025

Note: lnTC = natural logarithm of total clients; lnVAIC = natural logarithm of value-added intellectual coefficient; log_HCE = human capital efficiency; log_SCE= structural capital efficiency; log_CEE= capital employed efficiency firmage indicate age of the MFI. log_TotalAsset = size MFI measured interms of asset. Leverage= capital structure.

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics of all variables used in the study, including the natural logarithm of total capital (lnTC), value-added intellectual coefficient (lnVAIC) and its components such as human capital efficiency (HCE), structural capital efficiency (SCE), and capital employed efficiency (CEE) as well as firm age, firm size (logarithm of total assets), and leverage. The research draws on a sample of 21 microfinance institutions currently operating in Ethiopia and offering financial services. Using 10 years of data, the observed MFI was 210. According to Table 2, the mean lnTC is 9.2837 with a standard

deviation of 1.8714, indicating moderate variation in total clients across the sampled MFIs. The minimum and maximum values were 3.5553 and 13.0417, respectively, showing the presence of both small and large firms in terms of the total clients, they have served. The average \lnVAIC is 1.1219 ($SD = 0.6437$), indicating that for a 1-birr investment in value addition, MFI earns 1.1219 birr on average. This is a moderate level of value-added intellectual capital. The outcome reveals that the sampled MFIs used their intellectual capital resources moderately to achieve improved value. The observed range (0.0864–3.3289) further indicates considerable dispersion, suggesting that some firms are highly efficient in deploying intellectual capital, while others lag. This finding is consistent with (Chen et al., 2005; Firer & Mitchell Williams, 2003; Pulic, 2000) who reported wide variations in intellectual capital performance across firms and industries. From the elements of VAIC, Human Capital efficiency (\log_HCE) with a mean value of (0.9274897), indicating that for one birr investment in human capital, MFI generates 0.9274897 birr and significant variation ($SD = 0.6707911$), indicating that there are significant variations among MFI in terms of their Human capital investments. The minimum and maximum values (0.6707911–3.293598) demonstrate that some MFIs achieve improved value, while others are inefficient in utilizing employees' knowledge, skills, and experience. The finding reinforces the notion that, particularly in knowledge-intensive sectors, human capital often serves as the principal catalyst of intellectual capital efficiency (Maditinos et al., 2011) When we come to structural capital, the average value of SCE is 0.4066582 ($SD = 0.1728367$), with a minimum of 0.0125583 and a maximum of 0.6744128, indicating that MFI obtains approximately 0.41 birr from their structural capital, such as organizational databases, networks, and Information technology infrastructure. The standard deviation indicates lower variation in structural capital among Ethiopian MFIs; this similarity may be due to comparable regulatory standards. In contrast, CEE has the lowest mean (0.0581526) of capital employed by MFI, adding 0.058 birr from one birr investment, and a slight standard deviation (0.0733355), together with a minimum of 0.0004588 birr and a maximum of 0.7154408 birr, indicating that the tangible assets of the firms contribute less to value creation for MFI.

The control variable incorporated into the model indicates that the average age of an MFI is 17.12 years ($SD = 5.92$), with a range of 1 to 27 years. This distribution shows that the

sample in our studies comprises MFI with both young and old ages, which is a helpful way to examine how learning effects and resource accumulation change over time (Coad et al., 2016). The average log (Total Assets) of 12.31 (SD = 1.89) suggests that the firms in the sample are of medium size. The wide range (6.44–16.67) demonstrates that both small and large enterprises are represented. This allows businesses of different sizes to be compared meaningfully. The average leverage is 2.9295, and the standard deviation is 4.4649. It might be anywhere from 0.0333 to 61.4106. The high variation reveals that companies have quite different ways of structuring their capital. Some companies rely heavily on debt to finance operations, while others keep their debt-to-equity ratios low. This kind of difference is what the capital structure study finds: financial strategies are usually highly varied across industries and types of companies (Frank et al., 2009)

Heteroskedasticity Test

The study used the Breusch–Pagan/Cook–Weisberg test to test for heteroskedasticity. Greene, (2020) states that testing whether the expected coefficient is correct and whether the standard errors are unbiased are essential parts of the classical linear regression model.

Table 3 Breusch–Pagan / Cook–Weisberg Test for Heteroskedasticity

Model	Statistical Test	Chi-square (1)	Probability (p-value)	Decision
Model 1	Breusch–Pagan / Cook–Weisberg Test	1.76	0.1841	No heteroskedasticity
Model 2	Breusch–Pagan / Cook–Weisberg Test	0.69	0.4059	No heteroskedasticity)

Source; Authors, 2025.

Accordingly, the results in Table 3 indicate that model 1 and model 2 show chi-square (1) values of 1.76 and 0.69, respectively, and probability values of 0.1841 and 0.4059, respectively. The null hypothesis of constant variance (homoskedasticity) cannot be rejected as the p-value exceeds the conventional significance level of 0.05. This shows that the residuals' variance is identical across all the data, indicating that the model does not have heteroskedasticity.

Correlation Matrix's

Table 4 Correlations Between variables for Model 1

	log_VAIC	firmage	log_To~t	leverage
log_VAIC	1.0000			
firmage	-0.3486	1.0000		
log_TotalA~t	0.1927	0.4761	1.0000	
leverage	0.0822	0.1794	0.3314	1.0000

Source, Authors.2025

Table 5 Correlations Between variables for Model 2

	log_HCE	log_SCE	log_CEE	firmage	log_To~t	leverage
log_HCE	1.0000					
log_SCE	0.7174	1.0000				
log_CEE	0.0286	-0.1008	1.0000			
firmage	-0.3428	-0.2563	-0.1324	1.0000		
log_TotalA~t	0.2041	0.3312	-0.4045	0.4761	1.0000	
leverage	0.0865	0.0966	-0.0708	0.1794	0.3314	1.0000

Source, Authors, 2025

The correlation matrix indicates the strength and direction of the relationship between variables, ranging from -1 to +1.

In Table 4, Model 1 reveals that Value Added Intellectual Coefficient (log_VAIC) correlated with Firm age negatively ($r = -0.349$). Suggesting that a greater age of the firm may imply lesser efficiency of intellectual capital, attributable perhaps to rigidity or lack of current internal processes (Jameelah Maryam et al., 2012). On the other hand, however, there is an insignificant favourable correlation between log_VAIC and both leverage ($r = 0.082$) and log total assets ($r = 0.193$), indicating that the bigger and more leveraged companies may have more effective intellectual capital. The relationship between firm age and total assets is moderately positive ($r = 0.476$), suggesting that older businesses typically have more assets. Leverage has a moderate correlation with a company's total assets ($r = 0.331$) and a weak positive association with the company's age ($r = 0.179$).

Similarly, Table 5 also presents the correlation among the variables log_HCE, log_SCE, log_CEE, firmage, log_TotalA~t, and leverage. There is a high positive correlation

between \log_HCE and \log_SCE ($r = 0.717$), indicating these two components of human and structural capital efficiency tend to move together closely, likely reflecting complementing or reinforcing properties of intellectual capital inside firms. On the other hand, \log_CEE has very weak and even somewhat negative correlations with both \log_HCE ($r = 0.029$) and \log_SCE ($r = -0.101$). As we observe from Table 5, \log_HCE and \log_SCE have a moderate inverse relationship with the age of the firm ($r = -0.343$) and ($r = -0.256$), respectively. Signifying that when a company becomes older, human and structural capital efficiency may weaken either due to resource maturity or the inability to cope with new emerging trends over time. Additionally, business age reveals a moderate positive correlation with \log total assets ($r = 0.476$), consistent with the premise that older organizations tend to hold more assets, reflecting growth and accumulation. The variable \log total assets correlate favorably with \log_HCE ($r = 0.204$) and \log_SCE ($r = 0.331$), but adversely with \log_CEE ($r = -0.405$), showing that while larger firms may leverage human and structural capital more efficiently, their capital employed efficiency might decrease. Leverage demonstrates weak positive relationships with \log_HCE ($r = 0.087$), \log_SCE ($r = 0.097$), company age ($r = 0.179$), and \log total assets ($r = 0.331$), alongside a slight negative association with \log_CEE ($r = -0.071$). This implies that more indebted enterprises are partly associated with greater efficiency in human and structural capital and larger asset sizes, albeit the impacts are modest.

Multicollinearity

A collinearity diagnostic test was applied to assess multicollinearity in the regression model. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is a commonly used measure of multicollinearity. Greene, (2020) states that a tolerance value greater than 0.10, corresponding to a VIF less than 10, is an acceptable level of collinearity. Values in this range show that multicollinearity is not a significant issue in the regression analysis.

Table 6 Multi collinearity test for model 1

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
firm age	1.75	0.570998
log_TotalA~t	1.70	0.589947
lnVAIC	1.41	0.711135
leverage	1.13	0.888262
Mean VIF	1.49	

Source; Authors, 2025\

Table 6 presents the results of the multicollinearity test using variable inflation factors (VIF) and tolerance levels. Since the VIFs are below the commonly accepted threshold multicollinearity is not a concern among the independent variables included in the model.

Table 7 multicollinearity test for model 2

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
log_SCE	7.66	0.130539
log_HCE	7.45	0.134192
log_TotalA~t	2.26	0.443342
firmage	1.80	0.554184
log_CEE	1.29	0.772582
leverage	1.14	0.879847
Mean VIF		

Source; Author, 2025

We have also observed similar result in \

Table 6 presents the results of the multicollinearity test using variable inflation factors (VIF) and tolerance levels. Since the VIFs are below the commonly accepted threshold multicollinearity is not a concern among the independent variables included in the model.

Table 7 multicollinearity test for model 2. Multicollinearity is not an issue among the independent variables since the VIF result falls below the generally recognised threshold.

MODEL SELECTION

Table 8 Hausman test

Variable	FE (Model 1)	RE (Model 1)	Diff (b- B)	S.E.	FE (Model 2)	RE (Model 2)	Diff (b- B)	S.E.
lnVAIC / log_HCE	0.180	0.217	-0.036	0.015	0.327	0.317	0.010	0.022
Firmage	-0.064	-0.049	-0.015	0.008	-0.066	-0.051	-0.014	0.008
log_TotalA_t	0.415	0.410	0.005	0.030	0.420	0.415	0.005	0.028
Leverage	0.000	-0.000	0.001	0.000	0.001	-0.000	0.001	0.000
(Other Variables)	—	—	—	—				
log_SCE	—	—	—	—	-0.621	-0.427	-0.194	0.079
log_CEE	—	—	—	—	0.446	0.350	0.095	0.045
Hausman χ^2 (df)	33.09 (4)				32.77 (6)			
Prob > χ^2	0.0000				0.0000			
Preferred Model	Fixed Effects				Fixed Effects			

Source; Authors ,2025

According to Table 8, the Hausman test strongly rejects the random effects specification in Favour of fixed effects in both models (Model 1: $\chi^2(4) = 33.09$, $p < .001$; Model 2: $\chi^2(6) = 32.77$, $p < .001$), and RE estimates substantively diverge for these variables, adding additional evidence of misspecification under RE. Hence, we use the FE estimates for inference.

IV REGRESSION RESULT AND KEY FINDINGS

This section presents the results of the study based on the fixed-effect panel regression model. We specifically run the effect of value-added intellectual capital in Model 1. While the components of intellectual capital, such as Human capital, structural capital, and capital employed efficiency, regressed in the second model.

Table 9 **Fixed-Effects Regression Results for model 1**

Number of Observations	210				
Number of Groups	21				
Observations per Group	min=10, avg=10, max=10				
R-sq (within)	0.2663				
R-sq (between)	0.3077				
R-sq (overall)	0.2837				
corr(u_i, Xb)	0.1824				
F(4,185)	16.79				
Prob > F	0.0000				
lnTC	Coef.	Std. Err.	t Value	P>t	[95% Conf. Interval]
Variable					
lnVAIC	0.1805454	0.0815475	2.21	0.028	0.0196627 – 0.3414281
firmage	-0.064629	0.0191691	-3.37	0.001	-0.1024472 – -0.0268109
log_TotalAsset	0.4156916	0.0627295	6.63	0.000	0.2919345 – 0.5394488
levrage	0.0008435	0.0071155	0.12	0.906	-0.0131945 – 0.0148815
_cons	5.066326	0.526157	9.63	0.000	4.028286 – 6.104365
sigma_u	1.5807937				
sigma_e	0.37859468				
rho	0.94575293				
F test (u_i=0)	F(20,185) = 80.48				
Prob > F	0.0000				

Source; Authors, 2025

Table 10 Fixed-Effects Regression Results for model 2

Number of Observations	210				
Number of Groups	21				
Observations per Group	min=10, avg=10, max=10				
R-sq (within)	0.2796				
R-sq (between)	0.2901				
R-sq (overall)	0.2877				
corr(u_i, Xb)	0.1696				
F(6,183)	11.84				
Prob > F	0.0000				
lnTC	Coef.	Std. Err	t-value	P> t	95% Confidence Interval
Variable					
log_HCE	0.3274976	0.1530438	2.14	0.034	[0.0255404, 0.6294549]
log_SCE	-0.6217354	0.5672066	-1.10	0.274	[-1.740841, 0.49737]
log_CEE	0.446361	0.4671633	0.96	0.341	[-0.4753577, 1.36808]
firmage	-0.0660918	0.0190578	-3.47	0.001	[-0.103693, -0.0284905]
log_TotalAsset	0.4205995	0.0624342	6.74	0.000	[0.2974161, 0.5437829]
leverage	0.0010982	0.0070935	0.15	0.877	[-0.0128975, 0.0150938]
_cons	5.155864	0.532275	9.69	0.000	[4.105679, 6.206049]
sigma_u			1.5968626		
sigma_e			0.37719836		
rho			0.94715251		
F test (u_i=0)			79.78		
Prob > F			0.0000		

Source; Authors,2025

Value added Intellectual Capital (lnVAIC)

As presented in Table 9, Model 1 indicates that the coefficient for lnVAIC is positive ($\beta = 0.1805$) and significant at the 5 % level ($p = 0.028$). It implies that if the efficiency of intellectual capital increases by 1 %, the client size increases by about 18 %, keeping other variables constant. In other words, MFIs that emphasize the intangibles (human knowledge, structural processes, and relational networks) use their resources more efficiently and, as a result, reach out more widely, thereby increasing social efficiency. These results accord with previous studies. For instance, Ahamad et al., (2023) highlight that intellectual capital has a positive effect on the social outreach efficiency of MFIs worldwide (data cover the 2010–2018 period and 661 MFIs). - however, more substantial effects observed on financial efficiency. Likewise, Jameelah Maryam et al., (2012) found strong positive associations between IC and MFI performance in banking and non-banking MFIs. Our results, therefore, tentatively support the hypothesis that intangible resources, such as intellectual capital, drive social outreach in microfinance institutions.

Human capital efficiency (HCE)

Assuming all other factors remain the same, this finding indicates that HCE has a positive, statistically significant effect on client outreach ($\beta = 0.327$, $p = 0.034$), resulting in a 32.7% increase in outreach for every 1% increase in HCE, which implies better productivity in the sense that more efficient MFIs produce more outreach. Means that well-trained, motivated, and experienced staff increase MFIs' capability, making it easier to attract and serve more clients. The result is in line with previous research, which finds Human Capital Efficiency as the most dominant IC element in firm performance across both the financial and non-financial sectors (Ahamad et al., 2023; Bananuka et al., 2022). It is also consistent with studies conducted by Githaiga et al., (2023) who emphasise employees' knowledge and skills critical in expanding outreach (social performance) of MFIs. Therefore, the finding that HCE has a significant positive effect on Ethiopian MFIs is consistent with the extant literature, which emphasizes the crucial role of human resource quality in achieving outreach goals.

Structured Capital Efficiency (log_SCE)

For structural capital efficiency (SCE), the coefficient is slightly negative ($\beta = -0.622$, $p = 0.274$). The fact that structural capital such as systems, databases, and organisational routines has no significance means it does not directly affect outreach in Ethiopian microfinance enterprises. Some studies in the financial sector suggest that structural capital has a more minor or delayed effect on performance because organisational structures take time to improve productivity (Nadeem et al., 2020; Xu & Wang, 2019). When Ethiopian microfinance organisations invest in structural capital, they may place greater emphasis on compliance and reporting than on helping clients. If the results are very low, it could mean that the efficiency of the internal system differs from the performance of society as a whole.

Capital Employed Efficiency (log_SCE)

The study found a positive effect for Capital Employed Efficiency (CEE) ($\beta = 0.446$, $p = 0.341$), but it was not statistically significant. If you manage your money well, you can get more loans and reach more people. However, the results could be affected by institutional and financial limitations. This study aligns with Ahamad et al., (2023) A cross-national MFI study found that CEE is more associated with financial sustainability and profitability than with social outreach. These suggest that human capital is the most important component in accomplishing society's goals, even though improving capital efficiency may lead to higher profits.

Control Variables

Firm size, proxied by the log of total assets, is positively and significantly associated with social efficiency ($\beta = 0.4157$, $p = 0.000$) and ($\beta = 0.421$, $p < 0.001$) in both model 1 and model 2. This indicates that larger MFIs (in asset terms) tend to serve significantly more clients. In addition, larger MFIs are able to exploit economies of scale and deliver services to a broader client base, consistent with previous research indicating that size improves outreach and operational efficiency (Hasan et al., 2019)

Firm age, in both model 1 and model 2, however, shows a significant negative relationship ($\beta = -0.0646$, $p = 0.001$). and ($\beta = -0.066$, $p = 0.001$), respectively. A plausible explanation is that older MFIs may become more administratively rigid, less innovative, or shift focus toward financial stability and away from outreach goals, a phenomenon known as mission drift. This result is similar to that of Sangwan et al., (2023), who found a negative relationship between firm size and social performance of MFI.

Leverage does not significantly affect social efficiency with a very small positive coefficient ($\beta = 0.0008$) and ($\beta = 0.001, p = 0.877$) respectively in both models, which corroborates with earlier studies of Pide, & 2011 and Soltane Bassem, (2014) which noted that debt structure may affect financial viability but not necessarily social outreach.

V CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The main objectives of the study were to examine the relationship between intellectual capital and the social performance of Ethiopian microfinance institutions (MFIs). Panel data from 21 registered MFIs for a period of 10 years were observed between the years 2015 and 2024. According to descriptive statistics, there is a reasonable variation between MFIs in intellectual capital efficiency and client outreach, demonstrating the variation of institutions in utilizing intangible assets- intellectual capital to generate value. Among the components of intellectual capital, Human capital efficiency (HCE) proved the highest variability, implying differences in productivity of employees, skills, and experience, while structural capital efficiency (SCE) showed the least variation, likely due to standardized regulatory requirements within the sector. Capital employed efficiency (CEE) recorded the lowest mean, indicating that, compared to intangible assets, tangible assets played little role in value creation.

From the model result, aggregate value-added intellectual capital had a favourable and statistically substantial effect on total clients served(outreach) ($\beta = 0.1805, p = 0.028$), implying that improvements in intellectual capital efficiency enhance social performance.

Among the elements of intellectual capital mentioned, Human capital efficiency (HCE) exhibited a strong and significant positive relationship with client outreach ($\beta = 0.327, p = 0.034$), emphasizing the essential role of staff knowledge, enthusiasm, and output in expanding the client base. The finding is consistent with previous studies, which highlight human capital as the most influential in driving the performance of firms.

On the other hand, SCE showed a negative but statistically not significant association with client outreach ($\beta = -0.622, p = 0.274$), signifying that investments in structural systems may not immediately translate into improved social outcomes. Likewise, CEE disclosed a positive but insignificant effect ($\beta = 0.446, p = 0.341$), indicating that the use of physical and financial assets may contribute more to financial sustainability than to social outreach. Among the control variables, firm size had a positive and significant effect on outreach, while firm age demonstrated a significant negative effect, suggesting that older MFIs may experience reduced dynamism or “mission drift.” Leverage was not statistically significant, implying a limited influence of capital structure on outreach once other factors were controlled. Finally, both structural and capital employed efficiency demonstrated very limited influence; MFI should

mix them to make human capital vital for social performance and reach the broader financial inclusion goals of Ethiopian microfinance institutions.

Overall, this study has some inferences for both theory and practice. Theoretically, the findings of the study support the opinion that intellectual capital in general and human capital in particular are vital factors of social performance in microfinance institutions. This highlights the relevance of the resource-based view (RBV) and knowledge-based theory (KBT) in explaining performance differences among MFIs operating in developing economies such as Ethiopia. Practically, the manager of MFI gives priorities in human capital investments via providing capacity building, staff training, and other fringe benefits so that productivity and client outreach will improve. As a policy maker and regulator of financial institutions, the National Bank of Ethiopia should offer different initiatives, like digital capability and innovations within MFI, to enhance social performance (client outreach).

Although this study provides valuable insight into the relationship between intellectual capital and social performance of MF in Ethiopia, several limitations can be acknowledged. First, the study measures social performance via the total number of clients(outreach). This indicator captures only the breadth of service, not the depth of outreach, such as the poverty level of clients and female participation. Future research could employ a multidimensional social performance index. Second, the data obtained from 21 MFIs over a 10-year period are adequate for panel analysis; however, due to the existence of newly established MFIs, particularly smaller MFIs, there is a need for further analysis. Expanding the dataset to include more institutions or regional comparisons could enhance generalizability. Third, the study incorporates firm age. Size and leverage as control variables, other important variables such as governance structure and ownership, were excluded due to data unavailability. Future studies may yield a more inclusive and thoughtful understanding of what drives social performance.

V REFERENCE

- Adane Atara. (2023). *Microfinance Institutions in Ethiopia: Poverty Outreach and financial sustainability*. <https://journals.ju.edu.et/index.php/jbeco>
- Ahamad, S., Al-Jaifi, H. A. A., & Ehigiamusoe, K. U. (2023). Impact of Intellectual Capital on Microfinance Institutions' Efficiency: the Moderating Role of External Governance. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 14(2), 691–717. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-022-00937-8>
- Ayinaddis, S. G., Tegegne, H. G., & Belay, N. A. (2024). Does intellectual capital efficiency measured by modified value-added intellectual coefficient affect the financial performance of insurance companies in Ethiopia? *PLoS ONE*, 19(1 January). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0295321>

- Babelytè-Labanauskè, K. (2022). Re-exploring Seminal Works on Resource-Based View and Resource Dependence Theory: The Case of Entrepreneurial Research Organization. *Management of Organizations: Systematic Research*, 87(1), 21–42. <https://doi.org/10.2478/mosr-2022-0002>
- Bananuka, J., Nkundabanyanga, S. K., Kaawaase, T. K., Mindra, R. K., & Kayongo, I. N. (2022). Sustainability performance disclosures: the impact of gender diversity and intellectual capital on GRI standards compliance in Uganda. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 12(5), 840–881. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAEE-09-2021-0301>
- BEN SOLTANE Bassem. (2012). Social and financial performance of microfinance institutions: Is there a trade-off? *Journal of Economics and International Finance*, 4(4). <https://doi.org/10.5897/jeif11.129>
- Bhatia, A., & Aggarwal, K. (2015). Intellectual Capital and Financial Performance of Indian Software Industry: A Panel Data Analysis. In *Pacific Business Review International* (Vol. 7, Issue 8).
- Bontis, N. (1998). Intellectual capital: an exploratory study that develops measures and models. *Management Decision*, 36(2), 63–76.
- Chen, M. C., Cheng, S. J., & Hwang, Y. (2005). An empirical investigation of the relationship between intellectual capital and firms' market value and financial performance. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 6(2), 159–176. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14691930510592771>
- Costa, C. F. R., Nossa, S. N., Nossa, V., & Oliveira, E. S. (2022). The impact of investment in intellectual capital on firms' profitability. *Revista de Administracao Mackenzie*, 23(5). <https://doi.org/10.1590/1678-6971/eRAMR220147.en>
- Edvinsson, L. (1996). Developing a Model for Managing Intellectual Capital. In *European Management Journal* (Vol. 4, Issue 4).
- Firer, S., & Mitchell Williams, S. (2003). Intellectual capital and traditional measures of corporate performance. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 4(3), 348–360. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14691930310487806>
- Frank, M. Z., Goyal, V. K., Aggarwal, R., Flannery, M., Povel, P., Ritter, J., Strahan, P., & Strebulaev, I. (2009). *Profits and Capital Structure* *.
- Getachew Habtamu, T. (2023). The Effect of Intellectual Capital Efficiency on the Financial Performance of Commercial Banks in Ethiopia. In *Indonesian Journal of Business* (Vol. 1, Issue 2).
- Girma, B. (2017). Intellectual Capital Efficiency and Its Impact on Financial Performances of Ethiopian Commercial Banks. In *Research Journal of Finance and Accounting* www.iiste.org ISSN (Vol. 8, Issue 8). Online. www.iiste.org

- Githaiga, P. N., Soi, N., & Buigut, K. K. (2023). Does intellectual capital matter to MFIs' financial sustainability? *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*, 8(1), 41–52.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/AJAR-06-2021-0080>
- Grant, R. M. (1996). Toward a knowledge-based theory of the firm. *Strategic Management Journal*, 17(SUPPL. WINTER), 109–122. <https://doi.org/10.1002/smj.4250171110>
- Greene, W. H. . (2020). *Econometric analysis*. Pearson.
- Haque, S. M. I., & Weqar, F. (2021). The influence of intellectual capital on the Indian firms financial performance. *International Journal of Learning and Intellectual Capital*, 1(1), 1.
<https://doi.org/10.1504/ijlic.2021.10039514>
- Hasan Odowa, K., & Ali, L. (2019). Issue 1 www.jetir.org (ISSN-2349-5162). In *JETIR1901375 Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research* (Vol. 6). www.jetir.org
- Jameelah Hashim, M., Afizah Muhamad Arifin, N., Faizal Kamarudin, M., Rahim Khamis, M., Puncak Alam, K., & Selangor, K. (2020). Intellectual capital components and its relationship to Microfinance institutions' performance: The moderating effect of institutions specification. In *Advances in Business Research International Journal* (Vol. 6, Issue 2).
- Jameelah Maryam, H., Musa Alhabshi, S., Jameelah Hashim, M., & Abideen Adeyemi, A. (n.d.). *The Effect of Intellectual Capital on Microfinance Institutions Performance*.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/311535748>
- Jay Barney's. (1991). FIRM RESOURCES AND SUSTAINED COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE. *Journal of Managements*, 17, 99–120.
- Kamukama, N., Ahiauzu, A., & Ntayi, J. M. (2010). INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN UGANDA'S MICROFINANCE INSTITUTIONS. In *Augustine Ahiauzu & Joseph M.Ntayi. African Journal of Accounting* (Vol. 6, Issue 6). Nixon Kamukama.
- Kolachi, N. A., University, S., Haider, U., & Shah, A. (2013). BRICS Countries And Their Strategic HRD Agenda In 2020. In *International Journal of Management & Information Systems-Second Quarter* (Vol. 17, Issue 2). <http://www.cluteinstitute.com/>
- Le, T. D. Q., Ho, T. N. T., Nguyen, D. T., & Ngo, T. (2022). Intellectual capital–bank efficiency nexus: evidence from an emerging market. *Cogent Economics and Finance*, 10(1).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2022.2127485>
- Luh, P. K. (2025). Examining the effect of intellectual capital efficiency on microfinance institutions' performance: the case of a developing economy. *Management Matters*.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/manm-04-2024-0026>
- Maditinos, D., Chatzoudes, D., Tsairidis, C., & Theriou, G. (2011). The impact of intellectual capital on firms' market value and financial performance. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 12(1), 132–151. <https://doi.org/10.1108/14691931111097944>

- Mekonnen Akalu, M. (2024). The Intellectual Capital Performance of the Ethiopian Banking Sector. In *International Journal of Financial Management* (Vol. 14, Issue 1). <http://publishingindia.com/ijfm/>
- Memon, A., Akram, W., & Abbas, G. (2020). Women participation in achieving sustainability of microfinance institutions (MFIs). *Journal of Sustainable Finance and Investment*, 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20430795.2020.1790959>
- Moges Adugna, B., & Kumar, B. (2021). *Effects of intellectual capital efficiency on the financial performance of share companies; with the special reference of Ethiopian banks and insurance companies* (Vol. 25). <http://annalsofrscb.ro>
- Nawaz, T., & Haniffa, R. (2017). Determinants of financial performance of Islamic banks: an intellectual capital perspective. *Journal of Islamic Accounting and Business Research*, 8(2), 130–142. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIABR-06-2016-0071>
- Nicolescu, O., & Nicolescu, C. (2021). Stakeholder Management and Social Responsibility. In *Stakeholder Management and Social Responsibility*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003217701>
- Nik Maheran Nik Muhammad, & Md Khairu Amin Ismail. (2009). Intellectual Capital Efficiency and Firm's Performance: Study on Malaysian Financial Sectors. *International Journal of Economic and Finance*, 1.
- Nimtrakoon, S., & Tayles, M. (2015). Explaining management accounting practices and strategy in Thailand. *Journal of Accounting in Emerging Economies*, 5(3), 269–298. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAEE-02-2013-0012>
- Peñarreta Quezada, M., & Chavez Alvear, N. (2025). Impacto of Intellectual Capital on Financial Performance of Microfinance Institutions in Ecuador. *European Public and Social Innovation Review*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.31637/epsir-2025-1588>
- Pide, U. (2011). *Munich Personal RePEc Archive Efficiency Analysis of Micro-finance Institutions in Pakistan*.
- Priti Sharma. (2019). *Intellectual Capital and Financial Performance: A Study of Selected BSE S & P 500 Listed Firms ntrroduction*.
- Pulic, A. (2000). VAIC TM-an accounting tool for IC management. In *Int. J. Technology Management* (Vol. 20).
- Reed, K. K., Lubatkin, M., & Srinivasan, N. (2006). *Proposing and Testing an Intellectual Capital-Based View of the Firm*.
- Remer, L., & Kattilakoski, H. (2021). Microfinance institutions' operational self-sufficiency in sub-Saharan Africa: empirical evidence. *International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility*, 6(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40991-021-00059-5>

- Rong, C., Sial, M. S., Álvarez-Otero, S., & Jo, H. (2025). Assessing the Intellectual Capital of Value Creation Process of Commercial Banks in the European Union. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-024-02348-3>
- Sangwan, S., Nayak, N. C., Sen, S., & Sangwan, V. (2023). Does firm size affect client targeting? An investigation over the clients of the Indian Microfinance Institutions. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-01728-5>
- Sulaiman, E. A., Kasum, A. S., & Musa, W. A. (2021). INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL EFFICIENCY AND MARKET-BASED FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE: EVIDENCE FROM LISTED CONGLOMERATE COMPANIES. In *Corporate and Business Strategy Review* (Vol. 2, Issue 2, pp. 31–42). Virtus Interpress. <https://doi.org/10.22495/cbsrv2i2art4>
- Tahir, M., Quaid, S., Shah, A., Kong, H., & Afridi, A. (2021). *Intellectual Capital and Financial Performance of Banks in Pakistan*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352871468>
- Vetchagool, W. (2023). *Asia Social Issues The Effect of Intellectual Capital on Firm Profitability and Efficiency: Evidence from Thai Listed Companies in the Agriculture and Food Industry*. 16. <https://so06.tci-thaijo.org/index.php/asi>
- Xu, J., & Liu, F. (2020). The impact of intellectual capital on firm performance: A modified and extended vaic model. *Journal of Competitiveness*, 12(1), 161–176. <https://doi.org/10.7441/joc.2020.01.10>